

Investigation on Synthesis, Hypotensive Activity and Highly Selective Adrenergic Antagonistic Activity of some Simple and Substituted Indane Derivatives

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A few simple and substituted indane derivatives having $-C(=N)-N=$ terminal group in the form of amidoxime, imidazoline and tetrazoles as the pharmacophore were synthesised and were screened for hypotensive activity in rats. It was observed that nuclear methoxy substitution and chainlength of the indan-1-alkanoic acids impart profound effect on the yields of indanylimidazolines. Some of the compounds were found to be significantly active and two compounds on the contrary were found to be hypertensive. Some anomalous responses on autonomic challenge after administration of test agents lead to postulate existence of epinephrine-specific receptor system as the explanation.

AN indanamine (2a) synthesised for oral hypoglycaemic activity was found to be a β -blocker¹.

This observation led to the incorporation of the biologically important $-C(=N)-N=$ terminal group as the pharmacophore for activity² in the indane nucleus for the ability of this inert carrier to deliver a pharmacophore to the receptor site in a stereospecific fashion³. The $-C(=N)-N=$ terminal group was incorporated in simple and substituted indane nucleus in the form of imidazolines (3) and amidoximes (7). Exceedingly long (2-6 weeks) antihypertensive activity of Su-4029 after a single intravenous administration (30 mg/kg)⁴, high potency of Clonidine.HCl⁵, numerous other clinically useful 2-imidazolines, especially a report on 2-(2'-indanyl)-2-imidazoline as an adrenergic blocker comparable to yohimbine and phentolamine⁶ though discordant views is in record⁷, and on (-)-lofexidine—a stereoselective α_2 -adrenoceptor agonist—a highly potent antihypertensive agent⁸ made the amidoxime and 2-imidazoline terminal groups interesting. The corresponding tetrazoles (6) being carboxylic acid bioisosteres, though originally designed, synthesised and screened for non-steroidal anti-inflammatory activity⁹⁻¹², were included in the screening programme as they possess the required terminal group and because of reported antihypertensive activity of 5-substituted tetrazoles¹³⁻¹⁵. The present communication deals with the synthesis of the aforementioned indanyl derivatives (3) from indanylalkanoic acids (1) and 7 from 1 via the intermediate amides (4) and nitriles (5) (Scheme 1). These compounds together with the tetrazoles (6) were subjected to hypotensive screening test in normotensive rats.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in an Adco melting point apparatus and are un-

Scheme 1

corrected; preheated baths were used for compounds which melted with decomposition. Identity and purity of the compounds were ascertained by elemental microanalysis and spectral analysis. Uv, ir and nmr spectral data were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 uv-vis spectrophotometer, a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 297 spectrophotometer and a Jeol-JNM-FX-100 FT-NMR spectrometer respectively. Spectral data of all the compounds gave characteristic bands^{16,17}. Elemental microanalysis of all compounds conformed well with their proposed structures.

Indan-1-alkanoic acids (1a-f), the key intermediates, were synthesised by the general method of cyclodehydration of appropriate arylalkanoic acids

with polyphosphoric acid and subsequent reduction of the indan-3-oxo-1-alkanoic acids as reported earlier¹⁸, only phenylsuccinic acid was cyclised with anhydrous AlCl_3 ¹⁹. The amides (4a-f) was prepared from the appropriate indan-1-alkanoic acids (1a-f) via acyl halide intermediates by reaction with dry NH_3 following standard procedures^{9,11}. The nitriles (5a-f) were synthesised following the modified¹¹ or standard method of Mihina and Herbst²⁰ and adoption of the modified method resulted in excellent yields (~90-95%) of the acetone nitriles (5d-f). The tetrazoles (6a-f) were synthesised as reported earlier^{9,11}.

2-(Indan-1'-yl)-2-imidazoline (3a): This and other imidazolines were synthesised following literature procedures²¹. A mixture of 1a (8.1 g, 0.05 mol), ethylenediamine (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) and ethylenediamine.2HCl (3.4 g, 0.025 mol) was refluxed at 260° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and triturated with H_2O , filtered and washed free of basicity. The solid material was then treated with warm saturated NaHCO_3 solution, filtered, and washed free of alkalinity. The solid thus obtained (other imidazolines too) was treated with decolourising carbon and was recrystallised from aqueous MeOH to give 3a (27%, 2.5 g), m.p. 232-34° (Found: C, 77.08; H, 7.95; N, 14.96. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 77.38; H, 7.58; N, 15.04%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 260 (NH), 1 630 (C-N) and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3 ; TMS) 2.36 (2H, m, 2'- CH_2), 2.96 (2H, qn, 3'- CH_2), 3.37 (4H, t, 4-, 5- CH_2), 3.84 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 6.20 (1H, s, 1-NH) and 7.22 (4H, s, ArH).

2-(6'-Methoxyindan-1'-yl)-2-imidazoline (3b): A mixture of 1b (4.8 g, 0.025 mol), ethylenediamine (1.5 g, 0.025 mol) and ethylenediamine.2HCl (3.4 g, 0.025 mol) was refluxed for 6 h and was worked up (as described for 3a) to give 3b (9%, 0.5 g), m.p. 231-32°d (Found: C, 72.06; H, 7.67; N, 12.83. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_2$ requires: C, 72.19; H, 7.46; N, 12.96%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 260 (NH), 1 630 (C-N) and 1 185 cm^{-1} (OCH_3); δ (CDCl_3 ; TMS) 2.34 (2H, m, 2'- CH_2), 2.89 (2H, qn, 3'- CH_2), 3.38 (4H, t, 4-, 5- CH_2), 3.76 (3H, s, 6'- OCH_3), 3.85 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 6.26 (1H, s, 1-NH), 6.76 (1H, s, 7'-ArH), 6.80 (1H, s, 5'-ArH) and 7.14 (1H, d, 4'-ArH).

2-(Indan-1'-yl)methyl-2-imidazoline (3d): A mixture of 1d (5.0 g, 0.025 mol), ethylenediamine (1.5 g, 0.025 mol) and ethylenediamine.2HCl (3.4 g, 0.025 mol) was refluxed at 260° for 3 h or at 130-40° for 36 h, and was worked up (as described for 3a) to give 3d (2.0 g; for both of the reaction conditions) in 35% yield but the same reaction mixture when heated at 160-80° for 36 h yielded only 22% of 3d, m.p. 189-91° (Found: C, 77.82; H, 7.94; N, 14.24. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 77.96; H, 8.05; N, 13.98%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 266 and 273 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 280 (NH), 1 625 (C-N) and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3 ; TMS) 1.70 (2H, qr, 6- CH_2), 2.42 (2H, m, 2'- CH_2), 2.91 (2H, t, 3'- CH_2), 3.42 (4H, t, 4-, 5- CH_2), 3.62 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 6.18 (1H, s, 1-NH) and 7.10 (4H, s, ArH).

2-(6'-Methoxyindan-1'-yl)methyl-2-imidazoline (3e): A mixture of 1e (5.15 g, 0.025 mol), ethylenediamine (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) and ethylenediamine.2HCl (3.4 g, 0.025 mol) was refluxed at 260° for 3 h and was worked up (as for 3a) to give 3e (23%, 1.3 g), m.p. 182-84° (Found: C, 72.83; H, 8.16; N, 12.09. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{ON}_2$ requires: C, 73.01; H, 7.88; N, 12.16%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 230 (NH), 1 615 (C-N) and 1 195 cm^{-1} (OCH_3); δ (CDCl_3 ; TMS) 1.70 (2H, qr, 6- CH_2), 2.22 (2H, m, 2'- CH_2), 2.84 (2H, t, 3'- CH_2), 3.42 (4H, t, 4-, 5- CH_2), 3.56 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 3.76 (3H, s, 6'- OCH_3), 6.18 (1H, s, 1-NH), 6.70 (1H, s, 7'-ArH), 6.76 (1H, s, 5'-ArH) and 7.12 (1H, d, 4'-ArH).

Indan-1-amidoxime (7a): 7a and other amidoximes (7b-f) were synthesised following the literature procedures¹⁶. Dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (2.6 g, 0.0375 mol) and KOH (2.1 g, 0.0375 mol) dissolved separately in minimum volume of absolute EtOH were mixed. The precipitated KCl was filtered and washed with absolute EtOH and the washings were combined with the filtrate. 5a (3.58 g, 0.025 mol) was then added to the filtrate and was refluxed for 50 h while protected with a CaO guard-tube. EtOH was then distilled off under reduced pressure. The product thus obtained was extracted with 10% HCl and the acidic aqueous phase after Et_2O extraction was concentrated under reduced pressure and was then carefully brought to its isoelectric point by addition of dilute KOH solution, as evinced from appearance of turbidity. It was then allowed to stand in the cold for separation of solids to be complete, and filtered. The solid material was taken up in minimum volume of Me_2CO and was added cautiously to a large volume of hot H_2O . Separated solids were filtered and the filtrate was treated with decolourising carbon and was then concentrated and cooled to yield crystals of 7a (18%, 0.8 g), m.p. 157-58°d (Found: C, 68.29; H, 6.94; N, 15.68. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2$ requires: C, 68.16; H, 6.86; N, 15.90%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 580, 3 440, 3 315 (NH), 3 150 (OH), 1 650 (C-N) and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$; TMS) 2.17 (2H, qr, 2- CH_2), 2.88 (2H, t, 3- CH_2), 3.78 (1H, t, 1-CH), 5.30 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.21 (4H, s, ArH) and 8.40 (1H, s, NOH).

6-Methoxyindan-1-amidoxime (7b): Compound 5b (3.46 g, 0.02 mol) was added to NH_2OH solution (from 2.085 g, 0.03 mol of dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and 1.68 g, 0.03 mol of KOH) in absolute EtOH and was refluxed for 48 h. EtOH was then distilled off to such an extent that 7b (4.05 g) crystallised out of the reaction mixture in 98% yield. The analytical sample was obtained on treatment of this product with decolourising carbon and recrystallisation from C_6H_6 -MeOH, m.p. 141-42°d (Found: C, 63.88; H, 7.02; N, 13.71. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 64.06; H, 6.84; N, 13.58%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 470, 3 440, 3 350 (NH), 3 105 (OH), 1 650 (C-N) and 1 180 cm^{-1} (OCH_3); δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$; TMS) 2.24 (2H, qr, 2- CH_2), 2.82 (2H, qr, 3- CH_2), 3.68 (3H, s, 6- OCH_3), 3.82 (1H, t, 1-CH), 5.80 (2H, s, NH_2),

6.72 (1H, s, 7-ArH), 6.80 (1H, s, 5-ArH), 7.10 (1H, s, 4-ArH) and 9.22 (1H, s, NOH).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-amidoxime (7c) : A mixture of **5c** (2.53 g, 0.0125 mol) and NH_2OH (from 1.34 g, 0.0188 mol of dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and 1.1 g, 0.0188 mol of KOH) in absolute EtOH was refluxed for 37 h. EtOH was then distilled off to yield a viscous liquid which was extracted with dilute HCl. The acidic aqueous phase after extraction with CHCl_3 was carefully brought to the isoelectric point by addition of dilute KOH solution. The aqueous phase was then concentrated to yield a crystalline product on cooling. The solid thus obtained was treated with decolourising carbon and was recrystallised from a large volume of H_2O to give **7c** (36%, 1.05 g), m.p. 186°d (Found : C, 61.35; H, 7.15; N, 11.51. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 61.00; H, 6.83; N, 11.86%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 480, 3 370, 3 340 (NH), 3 130 (OH), 1 665 (C-N) and $1\ 185\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (OCH_3); δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS), 2.22 (2H, qr, 2- CH_2), 2.83 (2H, qr, 3- CH_2), 3.66 (1H, t, 1-CH), 3.70 (3H, s, 6- OCH_3), 3.74 (3H, s, 5- OCH_3), 5.23 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.79 (1H, s, 7-ArH), 6.85 (1H, s, 5-ArH) and 8.90 (1H, s, NOH).

Indan-1-acetamidoxime (7d) : A mixture of **5d** (3.14 g, 0.02 mol) and NH_2OH (from 2.09 g, 0.03 mol of dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and 1.7 g, 0.03 mol of KOH) in absolute EtOH was refluxed for 25 h. EtOH was then distilled off to such an extent that a crystalline product separated from the reaction mixture. The material was filtered and was treated with decolourising carbon and was recrystallised from MeOH-EtOAc to give **7d** (26%, 1.0 g), m.p. $200-01^\circ\text{d}$ (Found : C, 69.24; H, 7.36; N, 14.94. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$ requires : C, 69.45; H, 7.42; N, 14.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 385, 3 310, 3 280 (NH), 3 115 (OH), 1 660 (C-N) and $740\ \text{cm}^{-1}$; δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS) 1.96 (2H, m, 2- CH_2), 2.48 (2H, d, 8- CH_2), 2.88 (2H, qr, 3- CH_2), 3.38 (1H, t, 1-CH), 7.20 (4H, s, ArH), 8.88 (2H, s, NH_2) and 11.10 (1H, s, NOH).

6-Methoxyindan-1-acetamidoxime hydrochloride (7e) : A mixture of **5e** (3.74 g, 0.02 mol) and NH_2OH (from 2.09 g, 0.03 mol of dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and 1.7 g, 0.03 mol of KOH) in absolute EtOH was refluxed for 40 h. EtOH was then distilled off as far as possible. The resulting viscous liquid was extracted with 10% HCl. The acidic aqueous phase after extraction with C_6H_6 was concentrated to a small volume and by addition of dilute KOH was brought to its isoelectric point. The solid thus obtained was made free of H_2O and was taken up in minimum volume of absolute EtOH. The ethanolic solution was added dropwise to a cold ethereal solution of dry HCl with stirring. The crystalline solid thus obtained was filtered and dried under reduced pressure over KOH. It was then treated with decolourising carbon and recrystallised from MeOH-EtOAc to give **7e** (25%, 1.3 g), m.p. $182-83^\circ\text{d}$ (Found : C, 56.29; H, 6.55; N, 10.63. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 56.14; H, 6.67; N, 10.91%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 495, 3 420, 3 370 (NH), 3 105 (OH), 1 665 (C-N) and $1\ 195\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (OCH_3); δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS)

1.73 (2H, qr, 2- CH_2), 2.20 (2H, m, 8- CH_2), 2.78 (2H, t, 3- CH_2), 3.46 (1H, qn, 1-CH), 3.70 (3H, s, 6- OCH_3), 6.76 (1H, s, 7-ArH), 6.84 (1H, s, 5-ArH), 7.10 (1H, d, 4-ArH), 8.80 (2H, s, NH_2) and 11.04 (1H, s, NOH).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-acetamidoxime (7f) : Compound **5f** (2.71 g, 0.0125 mol) in absolute ethanolic solution of NH_2OH (from 1.34 g, 0.0188 mol of dry $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and 1.1 g, 0.0188 mol of KOH) was refluxed for 27.5 h. EtOH was then distilled off as completely as possible to obtain a gummy material, which was exhaustively extracted with hot H_2O . The cooled aqueous phase was extracted with Et_2O and then evaporated to dryness to yield a crystalline solid, which was treated with decolourising carbon and recrystallised from a large volume of H_2O , filtered and dried under reduced pressure to give **7f** (26%, 0.8 g), m.p. $116-18^\circ$ (Found : C, 62.34; H, 7.60; N, 11.08. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 62.38; H, 7.25; N, 11.19%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 565, 3 455, 3 265 (NH), 3 125 (OH), 1 662 (C-N) and $1\ 182\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (OCH_3); δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS) 1.86 (2H, qn, 2- CH_2), 2.41 (2H, m, 8- CH_2), 2.85 (2H, t, 3- CH_2), 3.40 (1H, qn, 1-CH), 3.86 (6H, s, 5-, 6- OCH_3), 5.56 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.76 (1H, s, 7-ArH), 6.81 (1H, s, 4-ArH) and 7.28 (1H, s, NOH).

Pharmacology : Overnight fasted normotensive albino male C.F. rats (150-300 g), pretreated subcutaneously with oxytetracycline.HCl for at least 5 days immediately prior to the day of the experiment, were anaesthetised according to the reported method²². The anaesthetised animal was set up for direct blood pressure and respiration recordings as described in literature^{23,24}. On stabilisation, the preparation was subjected to autonomic challenge procedures prior to and following administration of test agent at various intervals^{25,26}. Histamine and serotonin were also included in the challenge procedure. The challenge procedure was primarily designed for identification of undesirable actions and elucidation of possible mode of action of test agents. All the test agents were administered intravenously at 10 mg/kg dose level, dissolved in either 50% aqueous propylene glycol, or saline, or as Na-salts in saline. In the first instance, the preparation was always tested with a solvent blank. The dose and wash volume together was always 0.25 ml. The procedure required that the preparation should last for 4-5 h.

A compound causing a sustained fall of systolic blood pressure by at least 20 mm Hg was considered to be active. Clonidine.HCl (0.1 mg/kg) was taken as the reference drug.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the nuclear methoxy substitution and the sidechain length impart considerable influence on the yield of **3**. The yields of **3a** and **3b** from **1a** and **1b** respectively are lower than that of **3d** and **3e** from **1d** and **1e** respectively. Nuclear methoxy substitution, though far off, decreases the yield of **3** and compared to chain length this

TABLE 1—HYPOTENSIVE ACTIVITY AND AUTONOMIC CHALLENGE PROFILE OF SOME INDIAN DERIVATIVES

Compd. no.	Blood pressure (mm Hg±SEM)	Hypotensive activity (min) Onset Duration	Response to autonomic challenges after administration of test compounds (compared to control responses)										Inhibition score β'	Remarks			
			Control	% Fall	P	D	C	S	N	N/N	Epinephrine				I	β	
											α'	α''					N/ α'
3a	113.2±4.1	16.9±8.4 ^f	X	NC	NC	NC	±	1.36±0.18 ^f	NC	1.14±0.04 ^f	NC	1.20±0.12 ^f	NC	0.4±0.4	0.0±0.0 ^f	Inactive	
3b	122±6.0	7.7±2.8 ^f	X	NC	NC	NC	±	0.84±0.16 ^f	NC	0.58±0.02 ^b	NC	1.46±0.07 ^f	NC	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0 ^f	Inactive	
3d	118±3.1	14.4±4.5 ^f	X	NC	NC	NC	+	1.77±0.15 ^g	NC	1.76±0.56 ^g	NC	1.32 ^g	NC	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0 ^f	Inactive	
3e	121.7±4.3	8.9±5.9 ^f	X	NC	NC	NC	NC	0.95±0.27 ^f	NC	1.89±0.11 ^g	NC	0.50 ^g	NC	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0 ^f	Inactive	
4a	108±7.2	6.8±3.3 ^f	X	NC	NC	NC	±	1.40±0.08 ^f	NC	1.46±0.10 ^d	±	0.91±0.03 ^f	NC	0.75±0.75	-0.25±0.25 ^f	Inactive	
4b	112±2.0	23.5±4.0 ^b	X	NC	+	NC	±	2.16±0.26 ^g	+	1.61±0.19 ^g	±	1.41±0.27 ^f	±	1.0±0.58	-1.0±0.38 ^f	Active	
4c	109±2.7	27.6±4.0 ^b	X	+	+	NC	+	1.89±0.23 ^g	+	2.07±0.29 ^b	-	2.38±0.05 ^f	NC	2.8±0.2	0.0±0.0 ^c	Active,	
4d	114±4.3	25.7±3.9 ^b	X	+	NC	-	+	1.78±0.21 ^g	+	1.52±0.15 ^c	±	1.14±0.08 ^f	NC	1.25±0.75	-0.5±0.5 ^f	β -blocker	
4e	100±2.6	18.6±6.5 ^c	X	±	NC	-	+	2.23±0.28 ^g	+	2.03±0.23 ^g	-	1.09±0.06 ^f	NC	0.8±0.37	-0.4±0.4 ^f	Active	
4f	107±2.4	16.1±7.7 ^f	V	+	NC	-	NC	1.25±0.08 ^f	NC	1.22±0.18 ^f	NC	0.97±0.05 ^f	±	-0.2±0.2	-0.8±0.49 ^f	Inactive	
5a-f	NOT DONE																
6a	105±6.2	9.8±4.5 ^f	V	±	NC	±	+	1.53±0.28 ^f	+	1.50±0.37 ^f	-	1.09±0.09 ^f	NC	1.0±0.58	0.0±0.0 ^f	Inactive	
6b	118±4.9	22.1±5.3 ^d	~21	L	X	+	+	1.67±0.16 ^g	+	1.56±0.15 ^c	-	1.09±0.06 ^f	±	1.8±0.58	-0.4±0.24 ^e	Active,	
6c	110±4.0	29.5±3.5 ^b	~10	L	X	+	+	1.33±0.16 ^f	+	1.97±0.07 ^b	-	0.97±0.02 ^f	NC	2.0±0.52	0.0±0.0 ^e	β -blocker	
6d	109±6.4	19.4±3.5 ^d	~6	L	X	±	NC	1.57±0.08 ^d	±	1.56±0.30 ^d	-	1.33±0.21 ^f	+	1.2±0.37	-0.8±0.2 ^e	β -blocker	
6e	115±0.9	23.9±5.9 ^d	~16	L	X	+	+	2.34±0.81 ^g	+	2.01±0.56 ^d	-	1.13±0.08 ^f	±	3.0±0.0	-0.4±0.24 ^e	Active,	
6f	114±4.3	23.7±4.3 ^c	~3	L	X	+	±	1.92±0.24 ^g	±	1.56±0.17 ^f	-	1.27±0.12 ^f	NC	2.2±0.58	-0.2±0.49 ^f	β -blocker	
7a	111±6.7	4.2±7.7 ^f	Im	L	X	NC	NC	1.08±0.17 ^f	-	0.54±0.39 ^f	-	3.55±2.22 ^f	±	1.0±0.58	-0.25±0.25 ^f	Inactive,	
7b	120±3.4	5.1±3.0 ^f	~30	L	-	±	NC	1.01±0.13 ^f	-	0.47±0.12 ^g	NC	2.73±0.73 ^g	±	-0.22±0.22	-0.67±0.33 ^f	Toxic to respiratory system	
7c	124.8±8.1	0.52±4.9 ^f	V	L	NC	NC	NC	0.92±0.22 ^f	±	0.78±0.26 ^f	-	1.25±0.25 ^f	±	1.4±0.6	-0.6±0.4 ^f	α -blocker	
7d	115±6.1	9.0±6.4 ^f	V	L	NC	±	NC	1.67±0.41 ^g	NC	1.19±0.26 ^f	±	1.31±0.14 ^c	+	0.5±0.34	-1.17±0.4 ^e	Inactive	
7e	125.4±5.0	-18.7±2.5 ^b	Im	L	±	NC	±	1.66±0.26 ^g	NC	1.02±0.18 ^f	±	1.33±0.12	±	0.2±0.2	-0.4±0.24 ^f	Hypertensive	
7f	112.2±7.0	-7.9±2.7 ^e	Im	L	+	NC	±	1.77±0.73 ^f	+	1.63±0.46	-	1.02±0.01 ^f	NC	2.0±0.55	0.0±0.0 ^f	Hypertensive	
Clonidine	119.4±2.6	45.2±3.8 ^a	Im	L	+	X	X	2.00±0.49 ^e	+	1.72±0.57 ^f	NC	1.26±0.17 ^f	NC	X	X	X	

Probability values: ^a<0.001, ^b<0.005, ^c<0.010, ^d<0.025, ^e<0.050, ^fnot significant, ^gcould not be calculated. n=No of Experiments. X=Not done. C=Carotid occlusion for 30 s. D=Dimethylphenylpiperizinium iodide. I (β')=Isoproterenol sulphate. Im=Immediate. L=Lasts the entire duration of experiment. N=Control response to norepinephrine hydrogen tartrate. NC=No appreciable change. P=Phenylephrine hydrochloride. S=5-Hydroxytryptamine creatinine sulphate. V=Variable. α =Control response to epinephrine hydrogen tartrate. (\pm) (as used to denote change of response)=Barely perceptible potentiation; (+)=weak but distinct potentiation; (++)=moderate to strong potentiation; (±)=barely perceptible antagonist; (-)=weak but distinct antagonist; (-)=strong antagonist; (-)=complete blockade.

has a more pronounced effect as **1b** and **1e** give lower yields of imidazolines compared to **1a** and **1d**; and the reaction fails altogether with nuclear dimethoxy substituted **1c** and **1f** (not shown in experimental section). As biological screening data indicated non-indispensability of **3c** and **3f**, no attempts were made to synthesise these via other routes. It was observed that the reaction time can be substantially reduced by increasing the bath temperature from 130–40° to 260°. It was also noted that the amidoximes (**7a–f**) were not thermostable as these darkened on attempted drying at temperatures much below their melting points. This darkening also happened even on storage for long periods (months) of time at room temperature.

The results of hypotensive screening tests are summarised in Table 1. Each animal served as its own control for the test of significance of blood pressure values and data were analysed using Student's *t* for paired sets; Student's *t* for unequal groups and Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon signed rank test²⁷ was employed for α -blockade and β -blockade data respectively. Acetylcholine and histamine challenge data were excluded from Table 1 as these responses remained unaltered after the administration of the test agents.

Examination of Table 1 reveals a few intricate features of the test compounds. The amides (**4a–f**) resulted in sustained fall of blood pressure, and amongst these **4b–e** were significantly active. Possibly, being water-soluble the Na-salts of the tetrazoles (**6a–f**) elicited rapid onset of hypotensive activity which was biphasic in nature. For compounds, **4a, c–e** and **6b–f** the hypotensive activity lasted for the duration of the experiments. **6c** was found to be the most active hypotensive agents closely followed by **4c, d** and others; **4a–f** and **6a** were insignificantly active. The 2-imidazolines, **3a, b, d, e**, and the amidoximes (**7a–f**) were found to be insignificantly active and conversely **7e, f** were significantly hypertensive, **7e** being the more active one.

These results indicate the necessity of nuclear methoxy substitution for hypotensive activity, but dimethoxy substitution though beneficial was not a prerequisite. The $-C(=N-)-N=$ pharmacophore separated from the phenyl ring by one carbon exhibited maximum activity. Thus, the structural requirements for optimum activity were found to be (i) a one-carbon separation of the pharmacophore from the phenyl ring, and (ii) nuclear methoxy substitution. These structures also resemble the involved neurotransmitters fairly well.

Some of the test agents, notably **4d, 6c, e, f**, were found to antagonise the serotonin-induced fall of blood pressure. It is to be noted that these compounds resemble serotonin fairly well. A comparison with the potent antihypertensive, antiserotonergic irindalone and related *trans*-1-piperizino-3-phenylindans²⁸ and selective 5HT_{2A} serotonergic antagonism of 2-(alkylamino)tetralin derivatives²⁹ indi-

cates that appropriate modification of some of the test agents may lead to potential antihypertensive, antiserotonergic and antidopaminergic (D₂) agents.

However, the most interesting facet of biological activity of the test agents in general was found in adrenergic antagonistic activity profile. In view of β -blocking activity of **2a**¹ and very high selective α_2 -blocking activity of a series of tricyclic(aryl-oximo)propranolamines³⁰ and potent α_2 -adrenergic blocking activity of 2-(2'-indanyl)-2-imidazoline which compared well with yohimbine and phentolamine⁶, the test compounds were expected to elicit hypotensive activity mediated through anti-adrenergic mode of action. These observations also indicate that the structural requirements for the sidechain of β -blockers might not be as rigid as considered^{31,32}, and this may lead to a new class of β -blocking agents.

It was, therefore, not unexpected to find many of the amidoximes (**7a–f**) to be α_1 -adrenergic antagonists, **7b** being the most active amongst these, but on the contrary to expectation, none of these exhibited hypotensive activity. On the other hand, **7e** and **7f** were found to be significantly hypertensive. And, contrary to expectation, **7c, d, f** were found to antagonise β_2 -adrenergic fall of blood pressure and to augment isoproterenol-induced fall. **7d** was significantly active in potentiating isoproterenol-induced β_2 -fall and **7f** was found to antagonise epinephrine-induced β_2 -fall of blood pressure though not significantly. In this respect these were similar to **4c** and **6b–e**, i.e. in their ability to significantly antagonise epinephrine-induced β_2 -fall and spare or even potentiate isoproterenol-induced β_2 -fall of blood pressure. (Direct measurement and statistical comparison of β_2 -falls were not possible because of hypotensive nature of the test agents. Therefore, post-test agent β -responses to bracketed doses of epinephrine and isoproterenol were graded on an arbitrary scoring scale; where, none or barely perceptible antagonism=0, weak but distinct antagonism=1, strong antagonism=2, and complete blockade=3, the negative values indicated potentiation; taking into account the law of initial values of Wilder³³. The scores thus obtained were statistically compared using a non-parametric method²⁷). This selective β_2 -adrenoceptor antagonism takes quite long, often more than 3 h, to manifest itself. This delayed onset might be indicative of the possibility of involvement of some active metabolite(s). This differential β_2 -blockade is in consonance with the observation that substitution of a methyl group on the first carbon of the sidechain of dichloroisoproterenol caused a greater degree of blockade of peripheral receptors than cardiac receptors³⁴. The observation of Carlsson and Åblad³⁵ also lends support to our observation of differential blockade of the neurotransmitters, epinephrine, norepinephrine and isoproterenol, in presence of a blocker *in vivo*. The possibility of existence of further subgroups of α - and β -adrenoceptors has already been proposed^{36–38}.

It is to be noted that many test compounds and Elonidine HCl being hypotensive, naturally exhibited significant increase in the N'/N and α'/α values and, therefore, this aspect of these compounds remained untreated in this discussion. Compounds with differential affinity can be easily detected from the N'/α' values.

Expectedly, significant α_1 -adrenergic receptor blocking activity³⁹ was found in the amidoximes, 7b, d, e. Compound 7b was the most active one with a dose-ratio of $\sim 3.0-3.5$. Curiously enough, 7b did not antagonise norepinephrine-induced α_1 -rise of blood pressure and 7d, e effected potentiation of this response. All these compounds were also ineffective in reducing phenylephrine-, dimethylphenylpiperizinium-, and carotid occlusion-induced rise of blood pressure, whereas phenylephrine was weakly potentiated by 7d, f. All these observations indicate that the test compounds 7b, d, e are competitive α_1 -adrenoceptor blockers. Interestingly, none of these α_1 -blockers was found to possess hypotensive activity.

The above observations related to α - and β -adrenoceptor antagonistic activity indicate that the test compounds differentiated between norepinephrine and epinephrine with respect to their α_1 -effect and between isoproterenol, the 'specialist' β -agonist, and epinephrine regarding β_2 -effect. Keeping in view that the mechanism of maintenance of blood pressure by vasomotor centre is noradrenergic in nature⁴⁰, if the existence of an exclusively epinephrine-specific receptor system is assumed, the aforesaid seemingly contradictory observations can be easily explained. However, to establish this novel hypothesis, detailed pharmacological study of the test compounds is necessary. Furthermore, it seems likely that the test compounds exert hypotensive activity mediated through β_2 -adrenoceptor specific antagonistic mechanism. Detailed pharmacological evaluation of these compounds is in progress.

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